

INVESTIGATING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TEXTILE WASTE USED AS REINFORCEMENT IN ECO-FRIENDLY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study to make use of the waste textile fabrics to produce eco-friendly composites. Three matrices were selected for the study, namely agar, clay and mycelium. Textile fibres were used as reinforcement. 5wt%, 10 wt% and 15wt% of the fibre content was varied in the each of the matrices. The composites were tested for compressive strength, flexural strength and thermal conductivity. From the tests performed, it was found that the highest compressive strength was 4.9 MPa, obtained with of the agar composite. The agar composite with 5% wt fibre content had the lowest thermal conductivity.

KEYWORDS

Textile fibres, clay, mycelium, agar

INTRODUCTION

In Mauritius, the textile industry is a main pillar of the economy. However, it is also one of the most polluting sectors. One major problem of this industry is the generation of textile wastes. It is crucial to dispose of them in such a way that the environment is not affected. Economically, the cost of waste disposal is increasing. Moreover, based on a survey conducted among six major firms in Mauritius, it was found that there were three ways adopted for the disposal of their textile waste. They were either recycled, sent to landfill or given to recyclers for export. It was also deduced that about 1300 tonnes (58 %) of fabric waste was generated by these firms in the year 2015 (PAGE, 2017).

Worldwide, every year, about 5.8 million tons of postconsumer textile waste are produced in the European Union. It was found that only one quarter of the total waste were put to use, that is, recycled into low-value products and the remaining textile waste was incinerated (Briga-Sá et al., 2013). In 2017, a research work in the US showed that around 85% of textile are thrown away, which is about 13 million tons, that are dumped or burned. Each year, an estimated value of 92 million tonnes of textile waste is created globally. It is predicted that by 2030, more than 134 million tonnes of textile waste is expected to be discarded. As per statistics, only 66% of paper, 27% glass and 29% plastic PET bottles are recycled in the US. However, only 12% of textile waste is being recycled which clearly shows that the textile recycling industry is lagging behind (Beall, 2021). It is only recently that textile waste has been considered to be recycled and reused worldwide. The construction industry is one of the sectors in which the use of textile waste is being considered (Reis 2009).

Kamble., et al., (2020) stated that the efficient way of using textile waste is by using it in composites. Jayasinghe., et al., (2010) used textile waste in cement blocks while Reis, (2009) used them in polymer concrete due to the increasing waste disposal costs and the lack of natural resources. Moreover, textile material is also being used for the thermal insulating process of buildings.

Rubino et al. (2018) and Reis (2009) stated that in order to use textile wastes as a construction material, their engineering behaviour was needed to be studied which should show properties that attest to its quality. The structural and non-structural use of the material is defined by its mechanical properties (Reis, 2009).

Binici et al. (2012) showed that with an increase in the amount of textile fibre content the flexural strength increases. Anglade et al. (2021) showed that when fibres are added inside concrete slab, it causes the thermal conductivity and compressive strength to decrease. It has been found that this occurs because increase in fibre content leads to an increase in air bubbles in the composite, therefore leading to void inside of the concrete slab (Anglade et al., 2021).

For clay based composites, Kadir et al., (2016), stated that the compressive strength decreases when the coconut fibre content increases. Moreover, even with the least amount of coconut fibre (5 %), the sample prepared could not achieve the minimum requirement for the compressive strength test. When using Mycelium as matrix, it was found that addition of fabric does not contribute to a higher compressive strength due to fabric's soft texture and ability to bend (Silverman, 2018). Moreover, the flexural strength also decreases when the textile fibre increases within the mixture (Girometta et al., 2019). This is due to the bendable ability of the textile fibre and the presence of porosity within the brick (Girometta et al., 2019).

Disposal of textile wastes is a problem in many countries, If they are disposed in an open-air environment, due to its non-biodegradability criteria, people will tend to burn them, thus producing toxic fumes in the air. During the decomposition of some clothes that contain fibres like wool, ammonia and methane gas are produced. Methane contributes to cause greenhouse gas with a significant effect on global warming while ammonia which is a toxic gas is prone to affect both the terrestrial and aquatic environment. Economically, the cost of waste disposal is also increasing.

In this study, the use of textile waste as reinforcement in composites will be investigated in order to manufacture bricks for the construction industry in Mauritius. Different types of matrixes would be selected for this study so as to obtain a durable yet environment friendly biodegradable composite. Hence, an attempt to upcycle the textile waste would be made.

MATERIALS

Three types of matrix were selected based on their availability in Mauritius:

- Clay
- Biodegradable glue (Agar mixture)
- Mycelium

The composites were manufactured and the following properties were tested:

- Compressive strength
- Flexural strength
- Thermal conductivity

Extraction of Textile Fibres

The textile wastes, consisting of clothes, were collected. They were firstly sorted out and their buttons and zips were removed. They were then cut into small pieces of 1x1 cm to 2x2 cm and pulverised. The fibres extracted were in a fibrous form as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Fibrous textile waste extracted

Measurement of Textile Fibers

The diameter of fibres were measured using micrometry. The diameter of 70 textile fibres was measured with 5 set of data to produce replicates. The magnification of the microscope used, was x50, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The textile fibre

Preparation of matrix

Clay

The clay was processed using the wet method. It was locally collected and was immersed in water for 24 hours. The clay was then mixed with water until a smooth mixture was obtained. It was then sieved to 2 mm followed by 0.25 mm to remove smaller impurities. Sieved rock sand (sieve size of 1.2mm) and the clay were mixed to a proportion ratio of 1:2. Then, the mixture was sun-dried until a thick paste was obtained. For each 100g of textile fibres, 350L of water was added to pre-wet the fibres. The clay paste was added to the textile fibres and mixed by hand until a uniform distribution was observed. Then the mixture was placed in a mould and covered with a lid. The mixture was then compressed with 100kgf for 30s.

The sample was removed from the mould and was allowed to dry air for 24 hours. It was then placed in the oven at 60°C for 24 hours. After the sample was dried, it was cured in the furnace at 700°C for 2 hours. The sample thus produced was then polished using aluminium oxide rubbing brick . The resulting composite obtained is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Polished clay sample; (c) Levelling clay sample

Biodegradable glue

A biodegradable glue was developed from agar which was commercially obtained. It was prepared as followed:

- 1600 ml of water was warmed.
- Then, 12g of glycerine was added.
- 16g of agar was added and heated until completely dissolved.
- 112g of white flour was added to the mixture.
- The latter was stirred continuously until a syrupy mixture was obtained. It was allowed to cool.

The glue and fibre were then thoroughly mixed until uniform mixture was obtained. The mould was oiled up. The glue and fibre mixture were placed in the mould and a pressure of 10kPa for 1 minute was applied onto the lid of the mould. The sample was removed and then placed in oven at 60° for 3 days. Figure 4 shows the sample which was obtained and ready for testing.

Figure 4: Agar sample

Mycelium

For Mycelium, sterilisation of all equipment and tools to be used was first performed. Then, the mycelium, which was obtained from the Food and Agricultural Research and Extension Institute in Mauritius, was taken out and was broken into pieces. The pieces were directly used as a binder for the fibre composite.

The textile fibres and mycelium were weighed as per their percentage ratio. The mycelium and fibre were mixed and placed in the mould. A weight of 10 kgf was placed on each mould. The moulds along with their weights were stored in a dark room for 1.5 weeks. After one week the sample was turned over and allowed to grow further. The resulting sample is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Mycelium sample

Mould manufacture

The moulds used to manufacture the samples were made from hardwood. The sizes of the moulds are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Size of moulds

Type of test	Size of mould (mm)		
	Clay	Agar	Mycelium
Compressive strength	90x85x65	95x95x26	95x95x26
Flexural strength	90x85x65	130x13x10	130x13x10

Thermal conductivity	110x100x10	110x100x10	110x100x10
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Tests

Compressive test for clay

The Testometric M500-50AT Universal Testing Machine was used to perform the compressive test. The ASTM C67-05 standard with the following parameters were used:

- crosshead speed = 2.5mm/min.
- Load cell = 5000 kgf
- Preload = 5.0 N

The sample was placed in between two pressing discs, as shown in Figure 6. The test was started and the specimen was pressed until the it failed.

Figure 6: compressive test for clay

Compressive test for Agar and Mycelium sample

The standard used for Agar and Mycelium compressive test is ASTM C165-07. The parameters used were:

- Crosshead speed = 100.0 mm/min
- Load cell = 5000 kgf
- Preload = 5.0 N
- Final compression distance of sample = 5 mm

The sample was placed in between the flat plates fitted in the machine and the test was started. The specimen was pressed until it reaches a thickness of 5 mm, i.e. the sample was compressed to approximately 25% of its original thickness.

Flexural test for Clay

The Testometric M500-50AT Universal Testing Machine was used to perform the flexural test. The standard ASTM C67-05 with the following parameters were used:

- crosshead speed = 2.5mm/min.
- Load cell = 5000 kgf
- Preload = 5.0 N

A three point bend test was performed, as shown in Figure 7, by placing the brick specimen on the two anvils in the base fixture while the middle upper anvil compresses against the sample. The force was applied until the brick failed.

Figure 7: Flexural test for clay

Flexural test for Agar and Mycelium

The ASTM D790-07 standard was used for the flexural test on Agar and Mycelium bricks.

The following parameters were used:

- crosshead speed = 2.5mm/min.
- Load cell = 5000 kgf

Following the three point bending load mode, the sample was compressed until it broke. The data obtained was then recorded.

Thermal Insulation test for Clay, Agar and Mycelium

This experiment was set up to determine thermal conductivity of composites using the heat flow meter method. The standard ASTM C518 was used. A hollow insulating guard with internal measurement of 110 mm x 100 mm and thickness of 40 mm was constructed out of concrete, plywood and polystyrene. The sample was placed on the heater's surface. The temperature of the heater was increased to 80°C. When the desired temperature was reached, the insulating guard was placed. The set up was allowed to come to steady state over 30 minutes and then a thermal camera was used to read the temperature of the sample, as shown on Figure 8. The experiment was repeated for all the samples and the temperature was recorded.

Figure 8: Output temperature recorded on thermal camera

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Results

Diameter of Textile Fibers

The mean diameter was found to be 410 μm from a sample of 70 textile fibers.

Figure 9: (a),(b),(c) and (d) Microscopic view of the textile fibre

Figure 9 (a), (b), (c) and (d) shows the twisted microfilaments of the textile fibres. Most of the microfibrils are properly twisted to form a textile fibre, Figure (a) shows that some fibres are not well twisted and this led to voids in the composite leading to loss of strength.

Compressive strength

The mean results for the composite with different percentage of the textile fibres for agar, clay and mycelium matrices are shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Since, $CV < 1$ for all the results, it can be deduced that they are repeatable.

Table 2: Mean compression strength for agar based composite

Percentage weight of textile fibres/ %	Mean Compressive Strength /MPa	Std Dev	CV
5	2.338	0.275	0.118
10	2.918	1.563	0.535
15	4.916	0.746	0.152

Table 3: Mean compression for clay based composite

Percentage weight of textile fibres/ %	Mean CS/ MPa	Std Dev	CV
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5	4.770	2.332	0.489
10	3.615	1.460	0.404
15	1.348	0.639	0.474

Table 4: Mean compression for mycelium based composite

Percentage weight/ %	Mean Compressive Strength/ MPa	Std Dev	CV
5	5.047	0.641	0.127
10	4.354	0.458	0.105
15	3.656	0.459	0.125

Flexural strength

The mean results for the composite with different percentage of the textile fibres for agar, clay and mycelium matrices are shown in Tables 5, 6 and 7 respectively. Since, $CV < 1$ for all the results, it can be deduced that they are repeatable.

Table 5: Mean modulus of rupture for agar composite

Percentage weight/ %	Mean Modulus of Rupture /MPa	Std Dev	CV
5	0.371148	0.142252	0.383276
10	0.465278	0.028478	0.061207
15	0.575723	0.203346	0.353201

Table 6: Mean modulus of rupture for clay composite

Percentage weight/ %	Mean Modulus of Rupture /MPa	Std Dev	CV
5	0.435	0.364	0.836
10	1.415	1.627	1.150
15	0.180	0.036	0.203

Table 7: Mean modulus of rupture for mycelium composite

Percentage weight/ %	Mean Modulus of Rupture/MPa	Std Dev	CV
5	0.0593	0.0269	0.4531
10	0.0246	0.0158	0.6421
15	0.0246	0.0158	0.6421

Thermal conductivity

The mean results for the composite with different percentage of the textile fibres for agar, clay and mycelium matrices are shown in Tables 8, 9 and 10 respectively. Since, $CV < 1$ for all the results, it can be deduced that they are repeatable.

Table 8: Mean thermal conductivity for agar composite

Percentage weight/ %	Mean Thermal Conductivity/ (W/mK)	Std Dev	CV
5	0.3593	0.0463	0.1287
10	0.3660	0.0389	0.1063
15	0.4592	0.0296	0.0644

Table 9: mean thermal conductivity for clay composite

Percentage weight/ %	Mean Thermal Conductivity/ (W/mK)	Std Dev	CV
5	0.778	0.106	0.136
10	0.693	0.087	0.126
15	0.570	0.057	0.100

Table 10: Mean thermal conductivity for mycelium composite

Percentage weight/ %	Mean Thermal Conductivity/ (W/mK)	Std Dev	CV
5	0.463	0.032	0.068
10	0.446	0.019	0.042
15	0.380	0.019	0.049

Analysis

From the analysis performed, it was found that the agar composite at 15 % weight of fibre shows better compressive properties than that of mycelium and clay. The compressed 5 mm agar sample continued to have rigid properties although the sample was already compressed. For the mechanical property, Mycelium exhibits better mean compressive strength at 5 and 10 wt%. Clay did not show any improvement in its properties with an increase in textile waste content. This is in line with the results obtained by Kadir et al., (2016). This most probably occurs because of the air bubbles associated with the textile fibres which cause void inside the clay sample (Anglade al., 2021). Compared to bricks made of agro-waste materials (Madurwar et al., 2013), the highest compressive strength obtained with the textile fibres (4.9 MPa) is quite low. Murat and Paki (2008) used a combination of cotton wastes, limestone powder wastes, wood sawdust wastes and limestone powder wastes to obtain a compressive strength of 7 MPa. However, it is comparable to a mixture containing Portland cement, fly ash and rubber waste particles (Yilmaz and Degirmenci, 2009).

The flexural strength for clay and mycelium decreases as the fibre content in the sample increases. Silverman, (2018) stated that due to the fabric soft texture and the ability to bend, the increase in fibre content caused a failure for the mycelium sample. Clay brick also failed with an increased in fibre content because fibres create void in clay. Thus, it can be concluded that the porosity present in both clay and mycelium sample contributed to lower flexural strength (Girometta et al., 2019). Figure 10 show the presence of pores in the mycelium sample.

Figure 10: (a) mycelium with pores; (b) mycelium with textile fibre

Agar sample exhibited the best flexural property.

For the thermal insulation test, we can deduce that the thermal conductivity of mycelium and clay decreases as fibre content increases which is due to the presence of air that creates voids. The lower the thermal conductivity, the better the material act as an insulator. Therefore, it can be deduced that mycelium and clay are good thermal insulator with 15 % weight of fibre content. However, the thermal conductivity of the mycelium composite obtained in this study is much higher than that generally obtained for mycelium. Agar composite results in an increase in thermal conductivity due to its compact structure. As the fibre content in agar sample increases, the compactness of the sample increases and thus the percentage of void in the sample is reduced.

Overall, it can be deduced that mycelium acts as a good thermal insulator though the 5% agar composite has the lowest thermal conductivity. Agar also has good compressive and flexural strength.

CONCLUSION

The aim of evaluating the mechanical properties of the different types of composites with varying fibre content was met. From the results obtained and analysis performed, it can be deduced that the compressive strength of agar composite with 15 % weight fibre give better result. For clay and mycelium sample, the lower the fibre content led to higher compressive and flexural strength. The thermal conductivity test performed on the different samples showed that mycelium and clay act as better insulators when the fibre content increases. In the case of agar sample, the latter was found to be better with lower textile fibre content. Though the composites show low strengths, they can be used for non-load bearing members. The agar composite is being further developed to improve its mechanical properties so that it can be used for broader applications.

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